

The Cumulation of Methylmercury and Phenylmercury Species on Alga

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The cumulation of methylmercury and phenylmercury species on the alga *Chlorella kessleri* has been radiometrically investigated as a function of algal cells, the species studied and hydrogen ion concentration, in the absence and presence of different metal salts and complexing agents. It has been found that the cumulation factor F decreases with the increase of methylmercury and phenylmercury concentration and with the increase of pH , but is not influenced by the presence of metal salts. Reagents forming negatively charged complexes with methylmercury and phenylmercury cations decrease the F -value. The cumulation of species studied was quantitatively described using the affinity constants.

THE biotransformation of inorganic mercury, methylmercury and phenylmercury chlorides, has been investigated in our previous papers^{1,2} using different types of algae. It has been found that all species studied were cumulated very rapidly in the algae. However, from the second day onwards methylmercury and phenylmercury changed into less toxic inorganic mercury. In continuation of these studies, the physico-chemical investigation of the cumulation of methylmercury and phenylmercury species has been carried out to describe quantitatively the cumulation of the above species.

Experimental

All reagent used, unless otherwise stated, were of A.R. quality. Hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide, (superpure, Merck) were used for adjusting the pH .

Solutions for radionuclides (Amersham, England) were prepared by dissolving methylmercury-203 chloride (specific activity 2.5 GBq/g Hg) and phenylmercury-203 acetate (specific activity 2 GBq/g Hg) in 0.01 M NaOH.

Algologically and bacteriologically pure strains of the alga *Chlorella kessleri* were used in the experiments. The mean geometric volume of one cell, $V_a = 3.5 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^3$ and the mean geometric surface, $S_a = 4.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2$ were calculated from measured size of the cells.

Well-type scintillation NaI(Tl) counter was used for the measurements of the radioactivity and Radiometer PHM-52 (Copenhagen, Denmark) for the determination of equilibrium pH values.

The cumulation of methylmercury and phenylmercury species was investigated in the manner described earlier^{3,4}. An appropriate volume of alga suspension (containing a known amount of algal cells) was centrifuged and transferred into test tubes containing methylmercury or phenylmercury species (labelled with mercury-203), HCl (or NaOH),

different metal salts or reagents of known concentration (total volume 10 ml) and the mixture shaken for 1 hr. The equilibrium pH value, the radioactivity of algae (A_a) and that of the medium (A_m) were measured and the cumulation factor F (the ratio of the concentration of the species studied in alga and in aqueous phase) was calculated according to eq. (1)

$$F = \frac{A_a}{A_m} \frac{N_a}{N_m} \frac{V_a}{V_m} = \frac{D}{N_a V_a} \dots (1)$$

where N_a is the number of algal cells per cm^3 , V_a is the mean geometric volume of one cell in cm^3 , D is the distribution ratio of the species studied. All experiments were carried out at $22 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The influence of pH on the cumulation of methylmercury and phenylmercury species is illustrated in Fig. 1. At $pH < 7$, the cumulation practically does not depend on pH ; in these conditions methylmercury and phenylmercury are present predominantly as CH_3HgCl and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgCl}$ complexes. The decrease of the F -value at higher pH is probably connected with the formation of more soluble CH_3HgOH and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgOH}$ complexes. This assumption was confirmed by the fact that the addition of NaCl into alkaline medium leads to the increase of F -value. The kinetics of the uptake is rather rapid; the equilibrium was reached in less than 1 hr shaking.

It has been found that the F -values (in otherwise constant conditions) does not depend on the concentration of algal cells ($N_a = 7.5 \times 10^8 - 6 \times 10^9 \text{ cells.cm}^{-3}$). This allows the adjustment of the N_a value in such a manner that the measurement of distribution ratio is very precise.

The highest values of cumulation factor (F_0) or distribution ratio (D_0) were found at lowest concentrations of the species studied and at highest algal cells concentration. The increase of methylmercury

Fig. 1. The dependence of the cumulation factor F of methylmercury (curve 1) and phenylmercury species (curve 2) on pH (total concentration 3×10^{-6} mol. dm^{-3} , $N_a = (3.5) \times 10^6$ cells. cm^{-2} ; free points—1 hour shaking, full points—3 hours shaking).

and phenylmercury concentration leads to a decrease of the cumulation (F or D -values) because of the limited capacity of the algal cells to cumulate the species studied. Similar results were obtained in the study of the cumulation of alkali metals and alkali earths on alga⁴.

The cumulation of methylmercury chloride or phenylmercury chloride ($RHgCl$) on alga can be quantitatively described using the affinity constant K_M ⁴

$$K_M = \frac{[RHgClA]}{[RHgCl][A]} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $[RHgClA]$ and $[RHgCl]$ denote the equilibrium concentration of the species studied in alga and in aqueous phase, respectively, $[A]$ denotes the "free capacity" of algal cells to cumulate $RHgCl$.

The K_M value can be calculated from the following equations⁴

$$\frac{F_0}{F} - 1 = K_M [RHgCl] \quad \dots (3)$$

or at constant N_a and V_a :

$$\frac{D_0}{D} - 1 = K_M [RHgCl] \quad \dots (4)$$

The experimentally determined ratio D_0/D at different equilibrium concentration of $RHgCl$ (determined from the radioactivity in the aqueous phase) was used for the calculation of K_M values (Table 1).

It has been found that the F -value of methylmercury chloride ($pH \sim 5.2$ in the presence of $0.004 M NaCl$) also decreases in the presence of an excess of phenylmercury chloride. Similarly, the F value of phenylmercury chloride decreases in the presence of methylmercury chloride. On the other hand, F value of both the species is not influenced in the presence of $0.005 M Mg(NO_3)_2$, $Sr(NO_3)_2$, $ZnSO_4$, $CdSO_4$ or $0.001 M CuSO_4$, $Cr(NO_3)_3$. It follows from these results that the mechanism of the

TABLE 1—AFFINITY CONSTANT K_M OF METHYLMEURCY AND PHENYLMEURCY CHLORIDES IN $0.004 M NaCl$ ($pH \sim 5.2$)

Species	$\frac{D_0}{D}$	$-\log [RHgCl]$	$\log K_M$
CH_3HgCl	2.6	5.65	5.85
	4.6	5.40	5.96
	5.5	5.23	5.88
	14	4.85	5.96
	21	4.62	5.92
	50	4.50	6.19
		mean	5.96 ± 0.12
C_6H_5HgCl	3.5	5.85	6.25
	4	5.55	6.03
	6	5.50	6.20
	9	5.00	5.90
	24	4.96	6.32
	40	4.69	6.28
		mean	6.16 ± 0.16

accumulation of CH_3HgCl and C_6H_5HgCl is quite different from that of metal ions.

The stability constant of methylmercury chloride ($\log \beta_1 = 5.5$)⁶ and phenylmercury chloride ($\log \beta_1 = 5.8$)⁶ is rather high and because of this the cumulation of these species can be decreased only in the presence of reagents forming very stable negatively charged complexes with CH_3Hg^+ or $C_6H_5Hg^+$ cations such as sodium thiosulphate ($\log \beta_1 = 10.9$)⁶.

References

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